

QoS Management for XR Traffic in 5G NR: A Multi-Layer System View & End-to-End Evaluation

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Abstract—Extended reality (XR) applications are gaining a lot of momentum in the industry and consumer market. XR applications are characterized by multiple simultaneous data flows with different Quality-of-Service (QoS) requirements, imposing the need for advanced QoS management in 5G networks. Compared to 4G, the 5G NR technology has been designed with enhanced QoS support, by introducing the concept of QoS flows and an additional layer for QoS handling. However, recent studies show that additional QoS enhancements are needed in 5G to support the massive adoption of XR services. 3GPP envisions to include some enhancements for XR traffic in 5G-Advanced. In this paper, we review the current 5G QoS framework and study potential design improvements to fulfill XR QoS requirements in future cellular networks. We study QoS control procedures for XR traffics at different layers of the 5G NR protocol stack, including the proper configuration of radio access and core networks. In particular, we analyze various architectures for handling the peculiarities of XR, such as time-constraint and multi-flow applications. Also, we present XR traffic adaptation mechanisms at the application layer, to properly adapt XR traffic statistics to the actual 5G radio environment, and QoS schedulers for the MAC layer, leading to cross-layer performance optimization between XR application and 5G radio access network. Finally, we provide a validation study and end-to-end evaluation of QoS control mechanisms by simulating realistic mixed traffic scenarios in a 5G NR system-level simulator based on ns-3.

Keywords: QoS management, 5G NR, XR traffic, system-level simulations, XR loopback, QoS MAC scheduler, ns-3.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cellular networks have evolved over generations by incorporating new features and technologies in order to fulfill ever increasing requirements defined by the mobile network industry. A revolutionary path appeared with 5G that includes support for a variety of services with different Quality-of-Service (QoS) requirements [1], [2]. Thanks to that, the door has been opened for a plethora of new applications in different industry sectors. One of the 5G services that gained a lot of attention is the support for an immerse virtual 3D world with real-and-virtual combined environments and human-machine interactions generated by computer technology and wearables, e.g., as applied for digital twins in Industry 4.0. In this regard, the most important 5G media applications under consideration in the industry are eXtended Reality (XR) (encompassing Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and mixed reality) and Cloud Gaming (CG) [3]. XR and CG applications are characterized by stringent QoS requirements due to their

inherent time-critical nature. Therefore, it is extremely important to guarantee proper QoS handling for these applications.

QoS refers to the set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) by which the overall performance of different services can be quantitatively measured (e.g., packet loss, throughput, delay, availability, reliability, jitter) and which must be met so that the users in a network obtain a satisfiable quality-of-experience. Each service/application has its own relevant KPIs and associated QoS requirements. Even if 4G has set the basis for the QoS management of different services, 5G went one step further. The 5G Core Network (CN) and Radio Access Network (RAN) have been designed to specially consider and fulfill demanding QoS requirements of a variety of service flows across different and competing axis, by introducing the new concept of *QoS flows* at which QoS is enforced (see 3GPP TS23.501). This has led to a new QoS control and management framework, which will be further evolved in 5G-Advanced and 6G mobile networks. This is specially relevant for the case of XR/CG traffic applications [4], for which multiple service data flows with varying QoS requirements are generated for a single network device [3].

The capabilities of 5G NR, such as the new QoS model, have opened the door for the establishment of XR traffic as the immersive technology of future mobile networks. In fact, the study of service and operational requirements for 5G NR system towards the support of XR traffic started back in 2016 with 3GPP TS22.261, while in 3GPP Release-18, there are ongoing discussions/work items to provide XR-awareness in the RAN [5], i.e., to provide some XR application information to the 5G RAN for performance optimization, targeting power saving and capacity improvement techniques. Moreover, study of XR traffic in 5G NR scenarios has widely attracted the interest of the research community. Work is focused on various areas, such as XR traffic characterization [3], [6] and support of basic XR requirements through 5G NR field tests [7] and 5G system-level simulations [8]. However, work on 5G NR QoS management for XR traffic is currently on-going and related work is quite limited. The QoS provisioning for heterogeneous traffic is studied in [9] and [10], where the authors exploit neural networks and reinforcement learning for the determination of the optimal scheduling decisions and resource allocation, respectively. Despite the fact that these works address the QoS provisioning in XR and mixed traffics, they do not take into account all the peculiarities of XR traffic, such as the multiple flows with different QoS requirements,

TABLE I: Acronyms.

Abbrev.	Definition	Abbrev.	Definition	Abbrev.	Definition
5QI	5G QoS Identifier	MAC	Medium Access Control	RLC	Radio Link Control
AR	Augmented Reality	PDB	Packet Delay Budget	SDAP	Service Data Adaptation Protocol
CG	Cloud Gaming	PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol	SDF	Service Data Flow
CN	Core Network	PER	Packet Error Rate	UPF	User-Plane Function
DRB	Data Radio Bearer	PF	Proportional Fair	VoIP	Voice-over-IP
GBR	Guaranteed Bit Rate	QoS	Quality-of-Service	VR	Virtual Reality
KPI	Key Performance Indicator	RAN	Radio Access Network	XR	eXtended Reality

and therefore they cannot be fully considered as XR specific. Moreover, related work with respect to the study and analysis of XR traffic adaptation mechanisms in the context of 5G QoS management is scarce, especially considering the stringent XR QoS requirements under realistic 5G setups with highly fluctuating network conditions. It is worth noting that, in the video streaming literature, the collaboration between the transport system and the application layer to set the application data rates yielding a consistent service latency has been widely studied [11]. A relevant example is the L4S mechanism [12], standardized by IETF, in which packets are tagged to notify and identify congestion in the network, focusing on reducing the queuing delay (network latency), and which could be adopted for XR traffic adaptation.

Based on the above, in this paper, we focus on QoS provisioning for XR traffics in 5G systems, including the definition of adaptation mechanisms of the AR/VR/CG traffic configuration based on the instantaneous 5G NR RAN conditions, as well as XR-aware QoS MAC schedulers. We perform a cross-layer performance optimization between XR application and cellular RAN, which is extremely important to XR traffic given its unique traffic characteristics (multi-data flows) and strict KPIs (latency budget) as compared to legacy traffic. In particular, the main contributions of this paper are:

- We review how to handle QoS for XR/CG traffics and mixed traffic scenarios at different layers of 5G NR, as a way to provide XR-awareness in RAN and CN. For each layer, we have implemented the necessary procedures to support QoS provisioning for XR specific use cases, as well as XR traffic models, in the ns-3 simulator [13].
- We present a closed-loop mechanism for QoS control at the application layer, particularized for video streaming in AR/VR/CG traffics. The mechanism is called XR loopback and adjusts the application video codec rate based on the 5G KPIs. So, it enables the provisioning of RAN-awareness in the XR application, with XR application taking reaction to RAN feedbacks. The proposed XR loopback mechanism is a more general framework beyond L4S [12], because it can use different KPI metrics for traffic adaptation, without the need for packet tagging. Moreover, while congestion control mechanisms available in the literature (including L4S) focus on reducing the network latency, XR loopback can be used to improve also other QoS requirements, such as reliability.
- We introduce a generalized QoS scheduler at the MAC layer, which considers the priority levels, flow types, and packet delay budgets of the various QoS flows.
- We provide an empirical evaluation of various QoS management/control policies, using a dynamic 5G system-

level simulator developed in ns-3 (a.k.a., 5G-LENA) [13].

- The study and results of XR loopback in this paper show the benefits that cross-layer performance optimization bring for XR traffic and QoS management.

This paper is structured as follows. Sec. II introduces the QoS architecture and QoS characterization in 5G NR. Sec. III briefly describes traffic models for XR applications. Sec. IV presents QoS control/management policies for XR at different layers of the 5G NR system. Also, it highlights the implementation details to support QoS provisioning, with emphasis on the XR loopback mechanism and QoS MAC scheduler. Sec. V describes the simulation scenario and assesses the end-to-end performance. Finally, Sec. VI concludes the paper. Table I shows the acronyms most used throughout the paper.

II. QoS ARCHITECTURE AND CHARACTERIZATION

A. 5G NR QoS architecture

In 4G LTE, the QoS management was performed at the level of the Evolved Packet Service (EPS) bearer, and a one-to-one mapping between EPS bearer, S1 bearer and radio bearer was considered. Differently, 5G NR has introduced a more flexible QoS model through the definition of QoS flows. 5G CN and 5G RAN ensure QoS by mapping packets of service data flows (SDFs) to appropriate QoS flows and data radio bearers (DRBs). For that, 5G considers a two-step mapping process that decouples the roles of the CN and RAN (see 3GPP TS23.501). On the one hand, the 5G CN configures the mapping of SDFs to QoS flows. This process allows M:1 mappings, i.e., mapping of multiple SDFs to a single QoS flow (see example in Fig. 1). On the other hand, the 5G RAN independently decides how to map QoS flows to DRBs. For that, 5G NR has introduced in 3GPP TS38.300 a new layer in the RAN, the SDAP, focused on QoS flow handling. This process also allows N:1 mappings, i.e., mapping of multiple QoS flows to a single DRB (as illustrated in Fig. 1).

B. 5G NR QoS characteristics

The 5G NR QoS architecture supports three QoS flow types: 1) Guaranteed Bit Rate (GBR), 2) non-GBR, and 3) delay-critical GBR. As specified in 3GPP TS23.501, each QoS flow is classified using a QoS flow identifier in the network and it has associated a description with the following fields:

- 5G QoS Identifier (5QI) (used to indicate the 5G QoS flow characteristics, analog to the QCI in 4G)
- allocation and retention priority (containing information about the priority level, the pre-emption capability and vulnerability, thus allowing to decide whether a new QoS flow may be accepted or needs to be rejected)

Fig. 1: SDF to QoS flow and QoS flow to DRB mapping examples in 5G NR architecture.

- guaranteed flow bit rate (uplink/downlink), maximum flow bit rate (uplink/downlink), maximum packet loss rate (uplink/downlink), delay-critical resource type and notification, for a GBR QoS flow
- reflective QoS attribute (used to apply QoS in uplink traffic according to the QoS applied on the downlink), session-AMBR and UE-AMBR (to limit the aggregated bit rate per session and user), for a non-GBR QoS flow

The 5QI is an important QoS flow descriptor that indicates how the QoS flow needs to be treated through the NR protocol stack, or equivalently, how the RAN needs to be configured to properly serve each QoS flow. In particular, each 5QI addresses different services and indicates the following performance characteristics (3GPP TS23.501 Table 5.7.4-1):

- resource type (GBR, delay-critical GBR or non-GBR),
- priority level (P)
- Packet Delay Budget (PDB)
- Packet Error Rate (PER)
- maximum data burst volume (for delay-critical GBR)
- averaging window (for GBR and delay-critical GBR)

For example, conversational voice traffic has 5QI=1 and corresponds to GBR with $P=20$, $PDB=100\text{ms}$, $PER=10^{-2}$, and averaging window=2000ms. AR traffic has 5QI=80 (non-GBR) with $P=68$, $PDB=10\text{ms}$, and $PER=10^{-6}$. Interactive services for XR traffics with delay-critical GBR requirements can also be indicated with 5QI=87 or 88, which have $P=25$, $PDB=5\text{ms}$ (5QI=87) or 10ms (5QI=88), $PER=10^{-3}$, averaging window=2000ms, and a maximum data burst volume=500B (5QI=87) or 1125B (5QI=88). As such, the classification of the various traffics is performed based on the above described characteristics of the 5QI of each QoS flow.

III. XR TRAFFIC MODELS

3GPP has recently defined in [3] the evaluation methodology for XR studies in Release-17, including the traffic models, deployment scenarios, and evaluations. The objective

was to identify the limitations of current NR systems in supporting XR applications. Toward that objective, different traffic models have been defined for VR, AR, and CG applications. Among the AR traffic models one can mention the single stream (video) model for AR downlink and the multi-stream model for AR uplink, including various subvariants with one (video), two (pose/control + scene/video/data/audio) or three streams. There are two submodels for the three-streams AR uplink case; Model 3A uses aggregated streams for pose/control, scene/video and audio/data, while Model 3B considers pose/control, video I-stream and video P-stream. On the other hand, VR and CG traffic models include single stream (video) and multi-stream models (two streams, video + audio/data) for VR/CG downlink, and single stream for VR/CG uplink (using pose/control traffic). VR and CG models differ in the statistical characterization of the traffics.

To pursue the present study, we have implemented in ns-3 the 3GPP XR traffic models for AR, VR and CG. In particular, we have implemented pose/control, audio/data, and generic scene/video models, which can be parametrized to configure the various XR applications under single/multi-stream setups. A simulation helper allows combining various SDFs into a single PDU session for XR applications.

IV. QoS MANAGEMENT FOR XR

A. Application layer: XR loopback mechanism

All 3GPP AR/VR/CG models include a stream that follows a generic video model [3], in all of their variants (single/multi-stream cases). The video stream is modeled as a sequence of video frames arriving at the application layer according to a fixed video frame rate and a random jitter that follows a truncated Gaussian distribution. The size of each frame is also random according to a truncated Gaussian distribution. The statistical parameters for the frame size and inter-frame arrival time depend on two fixed parameters: the data rate (R , in Megabits/second) and the frame generation rate (F , in frames/second or Hz). Basically, the inter-frame arrival time is inversely proportional to F , while the mean packet size depends on the R/F ratio [3].

A way to control the QoS for XR at the application layer is to adjust dynamically the XR video codec characteristics to the available 5G RAN conditions. That is, the XR application can properly adjust the frame generation rate or the data rate, and consequently, the frame size and inter-frame arrival time statistics, depending on the radio environment. For good 5G RAN performance, the video quality can be improved by increasing the codec rate. On the other hand, for low 5G RAN performance, the video quality can be reduced to adapt to the poor conditions, with the final goal of improving the overall end-to-end 5G performance.

In ns-3 5G-LENA [13], we have implemented various XR traffic adaptation mechanisms, to adjust the XR video codec rate (by means of frame generation rate and/or data rate) based on 5G RAN level KPIs. As input to the codec adaptation algorithm, we can use various network KPIs such as packet loss/error, received data rates, packet delay or jitter. These measurements are collected over a time window (e.g., 500ms)

Fig. 2: XR loopback: closed-loop XR application traffic adaptation based on 5G simulator KPIs.

and fed back to the codec adaptation algorithm. Based on the KPI metrics, specific algorithms apply. An example algorithm is as follows: if the packet loss is below 2% then increase the codec rate, while if it is above 10% then reduce the codec rate. An illustration of the implemented XR loopback mechanism is shown in Fig. 2. The study of codec adaptation algorithms is out of the scope of this paper.

B. UPF: SDF to QoS flow mapping

The UPF maps SDFs into suitable QoS flows. This is done through the SDF/TFT traffic templates (see Fig. 1), defined by the operator. Ideally, a 1:1 mapping between the SDFs and the QoS flows (one SDF is mapped into one QoS flow) allows more granularity later on in the 5G NR RAN. However, in some cases, an M:1 mapping between the SDFs and the QoS flows is constructed (i.e., multiple SDFs are mapped into a single QoS flow). This may happen (and typically happens) in XR sessions, where the operator decides to map all the SDFs of an XR application into a single QoS flow. In this case, all the multiple XR SDFs go through the same QoS characterization (e.g., 5QI=80) and the same DRB in the RAN. For example, in the case of AR Model 3A, pose/control plus audio/data plus video/scene would go over the same DRB. Based on the above, we have extended the ns-3 5G-LENA simulator to support both 1:1 and M:1 mappings.

C. SDAP layer: QoS flow to DRB mapping

As previously mentioned, the SDAP is a new layer introduced in 5G NR to map traffic from QoS flows to suitable DRBs. The SDAP layer can have multiple SDAP entities, one for each PDU session (see Fig. 1). In case there is a 1:1 mapping between the QoS flows and the DRBs, then each DRB inherits the PDB, PER, and default priority level from the mapped QoS flow. Instead, for an N:1 mapping, each DRB has configurable PDB, PER, and default priority level, sourced from those of mapped QoS flows.

In the case of XR traffic, if the operator allows a 1:1 mapping from the SDFs to the QoS flows, then N:1 mappings

can be executed at the SDAP layer. For example, for AR, audio/data and pose/control flows can be mapped into a single DRB, because of their similar QoS characteristics. However, in case an M:1 mapping is executed at the UPF for XR traffic, then the SDAP layer does not have flexibility (there is a single QoS flow), and uses a 1:1 QoS flow to DRB mapping.

D. RLC and PDCP layers

Each DRB is handled by a single PDCP entity, as shown in Fig. 1, which may translate to one or two RLC entities depending on the RLC mode (RLC acknowledged mode has a single RLC entity, while RLC unacknowledged and transparent modes have two RLC entities, one for transmitting and another for receiving). The RLC and PDCP layers need to consider the QoS flow descriptions of the active DRBs to properly configure RLC/PDCP entities. For example, the PDB can be used to configure appropriate timers, such as the discard timer at the RLC/PDCP transmit entity and the reordering window timer for reassembly at the RLC/PDCP receiving entity. As an example, for 5QIs with a PDB of 10ms, both the discard timer and the reordering window timer should be set to at most 10ms. On the one hand, at the transmit entities, packets can be already discarded if their buffering time reaches the PDB. On the other hand, at the receiving entities, since reordering timers larger than the PDB could involve larger packet delays at higher layers (thus not meeting the QoS requirements), the reordering timer should be at most the PDB value. We have extended 5G-LENA to support the above described discard timers.

E. MAC layer: QoS scheduler

The MAC scheduler needs to consider the QoS flow descriptions of the active DRBs to perform the scheduling decisions appropriately (i.e., selecting the users to be scheduled and allocating physical resource blocks to them). For example, the priority level, resource type and PDB should be taken into account during the scheduling process to determine users with highest priority for scheduling and eventually perform the resource allocation to them.

Typically, the resource type is used to determine the way of selecting scheduling weights at the MAC scheduler. The scheduling weight (w) indicates the priority for a DRB to be scheduled. To encompass latency requirements and address mixed traffic scenarios, we generalize its computation as:

$$w = \begin{cases} (100 - P) \frac{r^\gamma}{R(\tau)} + F & \text{for non-GBR and GBR} \\ (100 - P) \frac{r^\gamma}{R(\tau)} D + F & \text{for delay-critical GBR} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where P is the priority level of the QoS flow carried in the DRB (see Section II-B), r is the instantaneous achievable data rate calculated by the spectrum efficiency and the channel bandwidth, $R(\tau)$ is the past average data rate updated within updated window size τ , $F = 100$ when the DRB has retransmission data and $F = 10$ otherwise, γ is a configurable parameter that balances between the actual and the past average rate, and D is a delay-aware weight related to head-of-line delay (HOL) and the PDB: $D = \text{PDB}/(\text{PDB} - \text{HOL})$. When

$\gamma = 1$, assuming the same priority for all users and ignoring D , the scheduler corresponds to standard Proportional Fair (PF): $w = r/R(\tau)$. The delay-aware weight D is an important factor for the QoS scheduler to meet tight XR latency budgets. The proposed QoS scheduler differs from traditional schedulers because it considers simultaneously the resource type, the PF metric, the priority, the PDB, and the HOL of each flow. Therefore, it promotes flows with tight latency requirements, while considering their priority level and maintaining certain user throughput fairness.

In the case of XR traffic, depending on the adopted SDF to QoS flow and QoS flow to DRB mapping architectures, a user may have one or more active DRBs at a given time. If there is a single active DRB per user, then the user's scheduling weight (scheduling priority) corresponds to that of the DRB. If there are multiple active DRBs per user, then the user's scheduling weight is the sum of all weights for each DRB.

For each transmission time interval, the users are ordered descendingly by their scheduling weight. The users with higher w (or higher sum of their w over active DRBs) are scheduled first. Note that in Eq. (1) a lower priority level value (P) indicates higher priority for scheduling.

Another important aspect to be considered in the MAC layer is the configuration of scheduling timings. 5G NR has introduced a new framework with dynamic scheduling timings (denoted by K_0 , K_1 , and K_2 , in 3GPP TS38.214 and TS38.213). These timers are configured at the base station by considering user processing times (i.e., how much time the user needs to process/prepare the data). However, depending on the amount of data to be served/received, and the variety of PDBs of various DRBs/users, the base station could relax the scheduling timers of specific users, as a way to ensure QoS for those with stringent PDB requirements.

Finally, to address stringent PER requirements, more robust adaptive modulation and coding procedures (e.g., reduce modulation order and/or effective code rate) and transmission repetitions can be used. The evaluation analysis of the flexibility provided by flexible timings, adaptive modulation and coding, and repetitions, is out of the scope of this paper, but they nonetheless form an important part of any QoS framework.

F. PHY layer

The PHY layer does not have as much flexibility as higher layers for QoS control. Still, some parameters can be configured to address different traffic/flow types. For example, suitable numerologies and their multiplexing can be properly selected to address latency-throughput trade-offs [14].

V. VALIDATION AND END-TO-END RESULTS

For the evaluation of the proposed QoS-based XR loopback traffic adaptation and QoS MAC scheduler, we use the ns-3 5G-LENA system-level simulator [13], [15], recently calibrated in reference 3GPP scenarios. We extended the 5G-LENA simulator with XR traffic models, QoS control at the application layer, the possibility to allow M:1 and 1:1 mappings at the UPF, PDCP discard timer, and the new MAC QoS scheduler (as described in Sec. III and Sec. IV).

Fig. 3: Multi-user mixed traffic simulation scenario.

We perform the evaluation under two steps. First we validate the XR loopback under a single-user scenario, and then we evaluate the end-to-end performance of XR loopback in conjunction with the QoS scheduler in a multi-user scenario. For the multi-user case, we consider a mixed traffic setup composed of 1 base station and 16 users, where 4 users run an AR application (composed of 3 flows, video+audio/data+pose/control), 4 users demand a VR application (1 video flow), 4 users play CG (1 video flow), and the remaining 4 users offer traditional VoIP traffic. AR video flow traffic is characterized by 5 Mbps data rate and 30 fps. For VR video flows, 30 Mbps data rate and 60 fps are used. For CG video flows, 20 Mbps data rate and 60 fps are configured. We use 5QI=80 for AR and CG, 5QI=87 for VR, and 5QI=1 for VoIP traffic. At the UPF, an M:1 mapping is adopted for AR. Fig. 3 shows the simulation scenario. Note that larger priority values P involve lower scheduling weights w for the QoS scheduler (see Eq. (1)).

Users are placed in a 50 meters random disk around the base station, following propagation conditions of the Urban Macro scenario using the 3GPP spatial channel model in TR38.901, with 75 MHz bandwidth in the 4 GHz band. Numerology 1 (30 kHz subcarrier spacing) is used. The base station transmit power is 43 dBm and the users' transmit power is 23 dBm. The base station antenna is composed of a 4×8 antenna array with 8 dBi gain, placed at 25 m height. Users have a single antenna element with 0 dBi gain, at 1.5 m height. The duplexing mode is TDD. HARQ incremental redundancy is adopted, with up to 20 HARQ processes per user. RLC unacknowledged mode is configured and the PDCP discard timer is 50 ms. The transport protocol is UDP. The simulation time is 20 s. Channel condition (LOS/NLOS) is updated every 1 s, and channel fading every 100 ms. In the simulations, we compare PF and QoS MAC schedulers, combined with the use (or not) of XR loopback adaptation. As KPIs we consider the end-to-end application layer throughput and latency.

The XR loopback adaptation applies to the video flows of all AR/VR/CG applications. We consider the following algorithm: If the packet loss is above 10% then the codec rate is halved (by 0.5), while if it is below 2% then the codec rate is increased by 1.1. The codec rate is increased/reduced by adjusting the packet size. A measurement window of 500 ms is considered.

A. XR loopback validation: single-user

The validation of the proposed XR loopback mechanism is shown in Fig. 4 for a single user with one video flow for CG

Fig. 4: XR loopback codec adaptation validation example.

application. For testing purposes, we consider an initial codec rate of 5 Mbps, with min and max values for the adaptation of 0.1 and 10 Mbps, respectively. Fig. 4 shows the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR), the packet loss, and the codec rate (application level) over time. Packet losses arise as a result of the SINR variations. As it can be observed, when the packet loss is very low, the codec rate is increased until its maximum value (10 Mbps). However, as soon as the packet loss goes above 0.1, the codec rate is quickly reduced, and it starts to recover (at a more slow rate) when the packet loss is below the acceptable margin for recovery, i.e., below 0.02.

B. Multi-user simulations: QoS scheduler + XR loopback

Considering a multi-user mixed traffic setup, we jointly evaluate the performance of QoS scheduler + XR loopback. The following min/max data rates are configured for XR loopback. For AR video, 0.5 and 10 Mbps are considered as min and max, respectively. In the case of VR and CG, 5 and 50 Mbps (min and max) are used.

Fig. 5 depicts the normalized end-to-end throughput and Fig. 6 shows the Cumulative Density Function (CDF) of the end-to-end packet delay (in ms), for each of the application flows separately (AR video, AR audio, AR pose, VR video, CG video, VoIP). They are displayed for the case of using PF vs QoS MAC schedulers, combined with the use or not of XR loopback (labeled as *wLB* for XR loopback, and *wolB* for without XR loopback). In the case of the end-to-end throughput, we normalize the values over the corresponding maximum downlink throughput for a given flow type (see Fig. 5) over the various schedulers and loopback mechanisms, to be able to compare proportionally all flow types. Note that VoIP traffic generates a very low data rate (and thus throughput) as compared to XR video flows. For packet delays in Fig. 6, we skip AR pose/control CDFs because of space limits; they exhibit a similar trend as AR video.

Fig. 5: Normalized end-to-end throughput.

Fig. 6: CDF of end-to-end packet delay.

A significant reduction of the end-to-end delays is obtained by using a simple XR loopback algorithm (see Fig. 6). Also, XR loopback allows serving the maximum throughput for all flow types (see *wLB* in Fig. 5). This is because the codec rate can be adequately adjusted for each user according to its propagation conditions, while ensuring low packet loss. Without XR loopback (see *wolB* in Fig. 5), just the throughput of VoIP can be fully delivered. This happens independently of the MAC scheduler (PF or QoS), because for both schedulers VoIP traffic has the highest priority (due to the highest priority level in QoS and lowest generated data rate in PF). Also, when using *wLB* as compared to *wolB*, a remarkable delay reduction is obtained for AR, VR, and CG, but the delay reduction is not so significant for VoIP. This is reasonable because VoIP traffic has priority over the rest of traffics and traffic adaptation through XR loopback is only applied to the video stream of AR/VR/CG applications. Let us note that the system capacity is the same when using *wLB* and *wolB*, but with no XR loopback, the system capacity is reached, thus leading to larger delays and losses, and which is shown to be

effectively resolved with XR loopback.

Comparing MAC schedulers, QoS scheduler gives more priority to high-priority traffic (i.e., VoIP and VR), thus improving their throughput and delay (see Fig. 5 and Fig. 6). In the 50% percentile of VR delay, a reduction of 35% is achieved for wLB and of 43% for woLB with QoS scheduler. As a counterpart, a slight delay increase is experienced for the rest of the flows (CG and AR) when no XR loopback is used. However, with XR loopback + QoS scheduler, all throughputs and delays are improved as compared to XR loopback + PF, just except for CG delay, since CG is the lowest priority traffic ($P=68$, as shown in Fig. 3) and can generate high data rates.

C. Lessons learned and vision

Overall, the proposed XR loopback has been shown to be an effective approach to control and optimize the end-to-end performance with QoS guarantees. Moreover, it is demonstrated that when combined with QoS provisioning, such as QoS scheduler, it results in improved performance across high-priority flows. With this work, we provide the research community with the means and baseline for future studies/analysis of enhanced and guaranteed QoS, with special focus on XR loopback mechanisms, in 5G and beyond networks.

Various techniques reviewed in this paper (such as QoS MAC scheduler, mapping architectures, scheduling timers, RLC/PDCP timers adjustment) are aligned with XR-awareness in RAN, under discussion in 3GPP Release-18 [5]. However, the proposed XR loopback mechanism is related to the reverse operation, i.e., to provide RAN-awareness in the XR application. The preliminary simulation shows the importance of cross-layer optimization between XR application and RAN, which aligns with the Release-18 XR enhancement directions.

We envision that QoS management in the next generation of cellular RAN should consider information exchange between XR application and cellular RAN for cross-layer optimization. Important factors to consider are how is the information defined and exchanged, and the QoS management granularity.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have presented a multi-layer system view of how to handle QoS for XR traffic and mixed traffic scenarios in 5G NR systems. We have started with a review of the QoS architecture and the QoS characterization in 5G NR, and presented the traffic models defined for AR/VR/CG applications in 3GPP. Then, we have revisited various XR-aware QoS control strategies at different layers of the 5G NR protocol stack, including SDF to QoS flow mapping architectures at the core network and QoS management policies at different layers of the radio access network (SDAP, RLC, PDCP, MAC, and PHY). Also, we have introduced XR closed-loop traffic adaptation mechanisms at the application layer and QoS MAC schedulers for XR in 5G systems. Finally, we have validated the XR loopback mechanism and presented end-to-end simulation results in a mixed XR traffic scenario, using an NR-compliant ns-3 based open-source system-level simulator. Results show that cross-layer optimization between

RAN and XR applications will be one of the key paradigms to achieve QoS of XR applications in future cellular networks. Future work includes the comparison of 1:1 vs M:1 mapping architectures, the joint optimization of XR loopback with other network layers' configurations (such as RLC/PDCP/MAC), and the evaluation of various XR loopback algorithms, using different inputs (e.g., packet loss and delay) and adjusted video parameters (e.g., data rate and/or frame generation rate).

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